

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№9

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 731 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-sentyabrda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate

Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor

Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor

Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)

Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor

Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Postdan xaridgacha: influenser va ilg'or veb-ilova (PWA – progressive web app)ning chakana sotuvga real ta'siri	14
Abdulaziz Madjidov	
Ta'lim xizmatlari bozori samaradorligini oshirishda ta'lim klasterlarining roli	22
Imamova Nilufar Asamutdinovna	
Korxonalar raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketingning tovar strategiyasidan foydalanish holati.....	29
Xidirov Sherzod Olimovich	
O'zbekistonda moliyaviy savodxonlikni institutsionallashtirish: NFIS, Finlit.uz va ta'lim islohotlari	34
Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	
Moslashuvchan menejment tizimlarini yashil iqtisodiyotga integratsiyalash tasnifi	39
Umarov Bezzod Batirovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsion marketing strategiyasini ishlab chiqish.....	43
Sheraliev Axror Sodiqovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida moliyaviy bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning tendensiyalari, undan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari va konseptual jihatlari	48
Roziqov Behzod Bahrom o'g'li	
Metallurgiya korxonalarida raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish chet el tajribasi	54
Abdullayeva Matluba Nematovna	
Исследование связи между восприятием изменения климата и внедрением устойчивых методов ведения сельского хозяйства в Узбекистане	59
Светлана Ражабова, Бахром Миркасимов	
Surxondaryo viloyati qishloq xo'jalik tarmog'ini barqaror rivojlantirishni iqtisodiy-ekologik modellari	68
Abdug'aniyev Otobek Allajonovich, Xo'jamqulov Bekzod Turdaliyevich	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda real sektor salmog'i va uning o'zgarish tendensiyalari	75
Mambetjanov Qahramon Qurbandurdievich, Isoilova Muhabbat Rustamjon qizi	
Qo'shilgan qiymatni soliqqa tortish uslubiyoti: xususiyatlari, vazifalari va muammolari	89
Xaitov Shuxrat Sharipboyevich	
Kognitiv yondashuv asosida tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalari grammatik va diskursiv kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning nazariy modeli va pedagogik texnologiyasi.....	94
Dadadjanova Feruza Muhammadyusupovna	
Transport tizimining rivojlanishi milliy iqtisodiy o'sishining asosi sifatida	98
Narziyev Umidjon Baxrillayevich	
Loyiha risklarini aniqlashda zamonaviy usullar va ularning samaradorligi.....	105
Marufhanov Davron Xasanovich	
Современные методы управления на железнодорожном транспорте в процессе трансформации системы.....	109
Кушакова Мамура Наримановна	
Финансовые механизмы и модели менеджмента в развитии устойчивой экономики транспортных компаний	115
Шарапова Гулчебра Рустамовна	
Kasbiy ta'limda o'quvchilarning raqamli kompetensiyasini shakllantirish va baholashning innovatsion yondashuvlari	120
Maxkamova Zuhra Tursunpulotovna	
Audit ishi sifati darajasini oshirish yo'nalishlari.....	124
Qushmatov Otaxon Qurbonaliyevich	

Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarda investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashtirishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari.....	131
Yuldashev Baxtiyor Gayradjonovich	
Ko'chmas mulk qiymatini baholash va uning ekonometrik tahlili	135
Jaloliddinova Mohira Alisher qizi	
Современные тенденции и вызовы бюджетно-макроэкономической политики в Узбекистане	142
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
Интеллектуал mulkda iqtisodiy mohiyat, mazmun hamda huquqiy jihat uyg'unligi	148
N.D.Maxmudova	
Axborot texnologiyalari asosida ta'limda loyiha boshqaruvida sun'iy intellekt va mashinali o'qitish imkoniyatlari	152
Xodjiyeva Durdona Abdurasolovna	
Концепция "Зеленого учета" и его значение для экономического развития.....	157
Умарова Зулайхо Турсуновна	
Iqtisodiyotning asosiy tarmoq va sohalariga kiritilgan investitsiyalarning joriy holati tahlili	166
Ismailova Kutlibeka Ulug'bek qizi	
O'zbekistonda yoshlar tashkiloti faoliyatini tashkil etishning o'ziga xos jihatlari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	172
Usmonov Adxamjon A'zamjonovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi maxsus iqtisodiy zonalarini investitsion holatini hududlar kesimida tahlili.....	178
Anvarxonov Abdulatifxon Jamshidxon o'g'li	
Kichik biznes va o'rta biznesni rivojlantirish orqali aholi farovonligini ta'minlash.....	184
Ahmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich, Nurqulov Nurbek Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Fiskal siyosat instrumentlari orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni qisqartirish va legallashtirish metodologiyasi.....	189
Ergasheva Malikaxon Avazxon qizi	
Fond bozorida savdo strategiyasi va uni amalga oshirishga yo'nalishlari.....	192
Soliyev Istam Ixtiyorovich	
Sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion rivojlantirishning asosiy tamoyillari	197
Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	
Iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda davlat boshqaruvi tizimining isloh qilinishi: Tajriba va istiqbollar.....	202
Mashrabaliyev Ibroximbek Mashrabaliyevich	
Iqtisodiyotning real sektorida investitsion loyihalarni moliyalashtirish amaliyoti.....	209
Qosimova Lola Sultanovna	
Sanoat mahsulotlari eksportida logistika zanjirining uzluksizligini ta'minlash: nazariy asoslar va amaliy yondashuvlar.....	217
Kurbonova Ma'mura Abdulkarim qizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligiga zamonaviy texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali qo'shilgan qiymat soliq ma'murchiligi bazasini kengaytirish yo'llari	222
Raxmonqulov Umidjon Rustam o'g'li	
Инновационные подходы к созданию проблемно-ориентированной системы прогнозирования, оптимизации и управления отраслями региональной экономики (жилищное строительство)	231
Далиев Ахтам Шарафутдинович	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati samaradorligini oshirishda UZEX faoliyatining joriy holatini baholash.....	238
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev, Mamatkulov Farrux Gulomjon o'g'li	
Sog'liqni saqlash tizimida tadbirkorlik faoliyatining turlari	244
Solikhova Dildora Alisher qizi	

“O‘ztemiryo‘lyo‘lovchi” ajning asisiiy faoliyatini samaradorligini oshirishda outsorsing xizmatini joriy etish strategik asoslari	250
Kaxarova Nilufar Yerkinjonovna	
Mintaqani kompleks rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari va ustuvor yo‘nalishlari.....	256
Jumayeva Zulfiya Qayumovna	
Sog‘liqni saqlash tashkilotarida xarajatlar samaradorligini ta‘minlash masalalari	260
Raximova Maftuna Axmadjon qizi	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida sof foydani taqsimlash bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan soliq solish masalalari.....	264
Suyunov Otabek Shuxrat o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekiston qonunchiligida raqamli transformatsiya jarayonida elektron to‘lov kartalarini soxtalashtirishni jinoyatlashtirish.....	276
Maxsadaliyeva Maftuna Toxir qizi	
Mamlakatimizda intellektual xizmatlar bozorini rivojlantirish masalalari.....	281
Miyassarov Davron Abdurashid o‘g‘li	
Validation of the dutch eating behaviour questionnaire (DEBQ) in a sample of uzbek women.....	285
Khursana Usmanova, Dr Muhammad Bilal, Dilafuz Qo‘chqorova	
Iqtisodiy xavfsizlik tizimlarini o‘ziga xos jihatlari	295
Nabiyev Bexzod Shavkatovich, Bayboeva Firuza Nabijonovna	
Davlat qarz siyosatini optimallashtirishda islomiy moliya instrumentlarining qo‘llanish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish yo‘nalishlari	299
Tilabov Nasrulla Tashmuratovich	
Роль институциональных структур фондового рынка в обеспечении финансовой стабильности.....	305
Камилова Севара Анваровна	
The Impact of Digitalization on the Management System in the Entrepreneurial Environment of Uzbekistan.....	309
Ibragimova Saida Ilkhomovna	
China’s Investment Strategy in Uzbekistan: Sectoral Trends and Strategic Implications (2013–2024).....	313
Maftuna Nuriddinova	
Qo‘shilgan qiymat solig‘i tushunchasi va uning iqtisodiy mohiyati	319
Eshkarayev Bobir Chariyevich	
Raqamli boshqaruvning afzalliklari va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	324
Xolbayeva Marg‘uba Qazoqboyevna	
Korporativ boshqaruvning nazariy asoslari: O‘zbekistonda qo‘llanish imkoniyatlari.....	328
Jumayeva Guzal Sherxon qizi	
Audit organizations in Uzbekistan	332
Razzaqov Jasur Xamraboevich, Yaqubov Matrasul Mavlonberdiyevich, Sabirova Nodira Komil qizi	
Xorijiy investitsiyalarning turlari va xususiyatlari	337
Gofurov Doston Boxromovich	
Mahalliy budjet mablag‘larining samaradorligini oshirishda auditning o‘rni.....	341
Primova Shaxnoza Komiljonovna	
Модели управления государственными финансами в зарубежных странах.....	345
Наимов Шохрух Шарофиддинович	
O‘zbekistonning sirkulyar iqtisodiyotga o‘tishi: yashil o‘shish indikatorlari tahlili	352
Hakimov Anvarjon Abdulloyevich	
Innovation management in the education system: practical challenges, international experience, and effective strategies based on the example of Uzbekistan.....	356
Imomov Inomiddin Abdulxamidovich, Egamberdiyev Farxod Botirovich	
Трансформация энергетического комплекса Узбекистана: текущее состояние и перспективы развития	363
Хмель Е.В., Мирджалилова Д.Ш., Дерюгина Е.А., Лозовская Н.А.	

Improving the efficiency of personnel management and optimizing labor costs in Sam Glass LLC.....	368
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Agzamov Avazkhon Talgatovich	
Interactive design and museum management: enhancing guided tours through IOT and virtual solutions.....	374
Ibrokhimova Aziza Abbasovna	
Hududlar investitsion jozibadorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	379
Imomova Kamola Novfal qizi	
“Innovatsion usulda baliq yetishtirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari (Sirdaryo tumani misolida)”	385
Bo'ltakov Sardor Oqbo'ta o'g'li	
Bank filial tarmoqlari samaradorligini baholashning xorijiy tajribasi va undan O'zbekiston banklari amaliyotida foydalanish imkoniyatlari	392
Xoshimov Og'abek Nizomjon o'g'li	
Zamonaviy iqtisodiyotda davlat xaridlarinin elektron savdolarning o'rni	398
Burxanov G'ofur Baxodirovich	
Реализация концепции развития рынка зеленой экономики в сфере экономической безопасности Республики Узбекистан.....	401
Юнусова Римма Рахманбердиевна	
Tijorat banklaridan “foйда” solig'ini undirishning bugungi holati.....	408
Ergasheva Lobar Raxmatulla qizi	
O'zbekiston oziq-ovqat sanoatini iqtisodiy rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	415
Abasova Gulirano Rahmatullo qizi	
Xorijiy tajribalar asosida ekologik tadbirkorlikning innovatsion va investitsion yo'nalishlarini tashkil etish	419
Turg'unova Tursunoy Maratovna	
Sanoat korxonalarini jozibadorligini oshirishda marketing strategiyasini amalga oshirish xususiyatlari.....	424
Raxmonova Feruza Musakulovna	
Turizm sohasida investitsion faoliyat: nazariy asoslar va amaliy yo'nalishlar.....	428
Ergashev Durdonaxon Aziz qizi	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida barqaror turizmning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va mavjud muammolar tahlili.....	432
Suyunova Dilnoza Mexridin qizi	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish jarayonida investitsion resurslarning mutanosib taqsimlanishi: samaradorlik va ustuvor yo'nalishlar.....	436
Otaboyev Feruzbek Oybek o'g'li	
Xususiy banklar faoliyatini rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning moliya bozoriga ta'siri.....	441
Abduqahhorov Asilbek Ahror o'g'li	
Mehnat resurslari tushunchasi, tarkibi va uning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	447
Kobilova Zebo Bobokulovna	
Xorijiy davlatlar tajribasida moliyaviy siyosatning makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi roli.....	453
Jabborova Dilafuz	
The impact of exchange rate policy on the financial-monetary system and economic growth.....	459
Raxmanova Laylo Baxodirovna	
Современные вызовы и модельные подходы к обеспечению конкурентоспособности банковской системы Узбекистана.....	464
Юлдашева С.Ш.	
Iqtisodiyotni innovatsion rivojlantirishda soliq mexanizmidan samarali foydalanish yo'llari.....	470
Ishimova Mohinur Absalomovna	
Innovative pathways for advancing sustainable tourism in Uzbekistan.....	477
Feruz Karimov	

Tijorat banklarida biznes subyektlari faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish yo'llari.....	482
Mirpulatova Luiza Mansurovna	
O'zbekistonda sanoat zonalarining rivojlanish bosqichlari va huquqiy-me'yoriy asoslari	488
Vafojev Akmal Ikromovich	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan samarali foydalanishda Germaniya tajribasi	493
Pardayeva Maftuna Ulug'bek qizi	
Korxonalar moliyaviy faoliyati bo'yicha auditorlik risklarini xalqaro standartlar asosida baholash	497
Shirinov Uchqun Abduxalilovich, Abduxalil-zoda Ra'no Muzaffar qizi	
Ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarining tarkibi va ularni pasaytirish usullari	501
Sodiqov Mirahror Abbos o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududlarini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda mahalliy budjetlarning ahamiyati.....	509
Sharopov Dilshodjon Raxmatullayevich	
The role of small business enterprises in enhancing the well-being of the population in Uzbekistan	513
Djalilova Shaxlo Ismoiljon kizi	
O'zbekistonda IPOlarni tashkil etish jarayonlari tahlili	518
Alikulov Azamat Tuygunovich	
Kichik sanoat zonalarini faoliyatining iqtisodiy-statistik tahlili (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida).....	522
Ozoda Batirovna Sakiyeva	
Hududlarning innovatsion turistik salohiyatini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	528
Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li	
Integrating circular economy principles in marketing and operations of grape export companies for green transition.....	534
Usmonova Diyora Mahmud kizi	
Foreign experiences of improving the quality of services in the field of tourism.....	541
Raxmonov Siyovush Turob ugli	
Z avlodining iste'dodli vakillari uchun raqobat: davlat boshqaruvi sektorining maqsadga yo'naltirilgan raqamli avlodni jalb etish strategiyalari.....	546
Nosirova Shaxzoda Bohodir qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida uglerod solig'ini joriy etish orqali soliq ma'muriyatchiligini takomillashtirish va yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishni jadallashtirish imkoniyatlari: ekologik, iqtisodiy va institutsional yondashuv	560
Jo'rayev Ahmad Saitnazar o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari reytingiga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar tahlili.....	566
Karabayev Nodir Abduhamidovich	
Budjet tashkilotlarida tuziladigan moliyaviy hisobotlarning ahamiyati.....	578
Norqulova Qutlug'nigor Oloviddinovna	
Методы и критерии оценки эффективности конкурентоспособности предприятия	582
Хусейнов Рахим Али оглы	
Zamonaviy HR texnologiyalarining korxonalar samaradorligiga ta'siri: "O'zbekiston temir yo'llari" AJ tajribasi.....	589
Xursanova Gulshan Ravshan qizi	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida innovatsion menejment strategiyalarining samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	593
Pulatova Dildora Abdushukurovna	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llashning bugungi kunda o'rni va ahamiyati.....	600
Xolmirzayeva Gulruxsor Maxammetovna	
Интеграция информационно-коммуникационных технологий в зеленую экономику: цифровые технологии для устойчивого развития.....	604
Бозорова Ирина Жуманазаровна	

Xorijiy mamlakatlarda tadbirkorlik subyektlari tomonidan mahalliyashtirish asosida mahsulot ishlab chiqarishning o'ziga xos jihatlari	608
Mirzabaev Xusniddin Muxamadjonovich	
Цифровизация зеленой экономики: синергия технологий для устойчивого будущего	616
Мухамадиева Кибриё Баходировна, Умарова Надира Рахмановна, Шарипова Зулфия Шокиржоновна, Эшпулатова Хусния Мирғолиб кизи	
O'zbekistonda to'qimachilik mahsulotlari bozori va rivojlanishi	621
Alimxodjayeva Nargiza Elshodovna	
Samarqand viloyatida tikuv-to'qimachilik sanoatining rivojlanish holati va ishlab chiqarish hajmining prognozi.....	629
Ikramova Taxmina Latifovna	
Повышение эффективности управления рисками в проектах государственно-частного партнерства в сфере услуг	639
Айтбаева Гульзада Куанышбаевна	
Surxondaryo viloyati iqtisodiy o'sish darajalarini ekonometrik modellashtirish	645
Pardayeva Ma'rifat Muzaffarovna	
Зарубежный опыт развития экономики ресурсно-сырьевых регионов: модели диверсификации и возможности адаптации.....	654
Севара Кахрамоновна Хакбердиева	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishning ahamiyati.....	658
Abduvoxidova Mohinur Akmalovna	
O'zbekiston sug'urta bozorida esg va yashil moliya instrumentlaridan foydalanish holati va imkoniyatlari.....	662
Zoyirov Laziz Subxonovich	
Xorazm viloyatida transport xizmatlari ko'rsatishning amaldagi holati tahlili va uni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	668
Sharipova Bibijon Baxtiyorovna	
Ulgurji savdo qoidalari va chakana savdodan farqli tomonlari	678
Batirova Raxima Abdujabbarovna, Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich	
Xalqaro integratsiya jarayonlarida raqamli iqtisodiyotning o'rni.....	684
Zaripov Xurshid Zakir o'g'li	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromadlari va xarajatlarining hozirgi holati	690
Himmatov Abdisamat Xalilovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida aholining moliyaviy madaniyatini rivojlantirish muammolari va istiqbollari.....	696
Abdurazakova Nargiza Rixsibayevna	
Цели устойчивого развития и роль цифровых платформ в сфере трудовой миграции	702
Газиёва Сулхия Саидмашрафовна	
Onlayn savdo maydonchalarida mijoz sodiqligini shakllantirishda marketing strategiyalarining o'rni.....	706
Vaxromov Xudoyor Xabibullo o'g'li	
Методологические основы оценки эффективности «зеленых» технологий в строительном секторе.....	710
Тожиева Дилфуза Бабамуратовна	
Korxonalarda moliyaviy instrumentlar auditi masalalarini rivojlantirish.....	715
Mahmudov Saidjamol Kadirjanovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi soliq ma'murchiligini takomillashtirish jarayonlari	722
Mahmudova Sevara Rahmat qizi, Alardonov Muxammadali Ibragimovich	
Improving the efficiency of modern housing fund management system	726
D.A. Berdiyeva, Aminova Naima Umar qizi	

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF MODERN HOUSING FUND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

D.A. Berdiyeva

PhD, Professor

Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering

Aminova Naima Umar qizi

Trainee-teacher of the Department of

“Economics, Accounting and Audit”

of the TASHKENT BRANCH of SAMDVMCHBU

Annotatsiya: This article examines strategies to improve the efficiency of modern housing management systems in the context of urbanization, digital transformation, and sustainable development. A review of existing literature, including international experiences and national studies, highlights the importance of integrated approaches to managing housing stock. Methodological tools such as performance indicators, cost–benefit analysis, and smart technologies are analyzed. Results demonstrate that effective management relies on transparency, resident participation, innovative financing, and digitalization. The discussion emphasizes the role of governance reforms and international best practices in strengthening efficiency. The study concludes that enhancing housing management efficiency is crucial for ensuring sustainable urban development, improving service quality, and addressing social needs.

Kalit so'zlar: housing management, efficiency, urbanization, governance, sustainability, infrastructure, innovation, financing, digitalization, participation, performance.

Abstract: Ushbu maqolada urbanizatsiya, raqamli transformatsiya va barqaror rivojlanish sharoitida zamonaviy uy-joy boshqaruvi tizimlarining samaradorligini oshirish strategiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Xalqaro tajribalar va milliy tadqiqotlarni o'z ichiga olgan mavjud adabiyotlar sharhi uy-joy fondini boshqarishda kompleks yondashuvlarning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Metodologik vositalar sifatida samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlari, xarajat–foйда tahlili va aqlli texnologiyalar tahlil qilinadi. Natijalar samarali boshqaruvning shaffoflik, aholi ishtiroki, innovatsion moliyalashtirish va raqamlashtirishga tayanganini ko'rsatadi. Muhokama qismida samaradorlikni oshirishda boshqaruv islohotlari va xalqaro ilg'or tajribalarning o'rni ta'kidlanadi. Tadqiqot xulosasiga ko'ra, uy-joy boshqaruvi samaradorligini oshirish barqaror shahar rivojlanishini ta'minlash, xizmatlar sifatini yaxshilash va ijtimoiy ehtiyojlarni qondirish uchun muhimdir.

Key words: uy-joy boshqaruvi, samaradorlik, urbanizatsiya, boshqaruv, barqarorlik, infratuzilma, innovatsiya, moliyalashtirish, raqamlashtirish, ishtirok, samaradorlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются стратегии повышения эффективности современных систем управления жилищным фондом в условиях урбанизации, цифровой трансформации и устойчивого развития. Обзор существующей литературы, включая международный опыт и национальные исследования, подчеркивает важность комплексных подходов к управлению жилищным фондом. В качестве методологических инструментов анализируются показатели эффективности, анализ «затраты–выгоды» и умные технологии. Результаты показывают, что эффективное управление основывается на прозрачности, участии жителей, инновационном финансировании и цифровизации. В дискуссии акцентируется роль управленческих реформ и международной практики в повышении эффективности. В заключении подчеркивается, что улучшение эффективности управления жильем имеет решающее значение для обеспечения устойчивого городского развития, повышения качества услуг и удовлетворения социальных потребностей.

Ключевые слова: управление жильем, эффективность, урбанизация, управление, устойчивость, инфраструктура, инновации, финансирование, цифровизация, участие, результативность.

INTRODUCTION

The management of modern housing stock has become one of the most pressing issues in the context of rapid urbanization, demographic growth, and increasing demands for quality communal services. In Uzbekistan, as in many other countries undergoing structural reforms, the housing and communal services (HCS) sector is central to socio-economic stability, citizens' quality of life, and sustainable urban development. The effectiveness of housing stock management systems is directly linked to the optimization of resource use, the integration of innovative technologies, and the ability to provide reliable and affordable services to the population.

Globally, housing management is increasingly shaped by digitalization, public-private partnerships, and sustainability requirements. According to UN-Habitat (2020), effective housing management is a cornerstone of inclusive and resilient urban development, as it ensures access to adequate housing while promoting environmental and economic sustainability. Similarly, the OECD (2021) emphasizes that housing management efficiency directly affects social equity, labor mobility, and overall economic competitiveness.

In Uzbekistan, recent reforms reflect a growing commitment to strengthening this sector. Government strategies prioritize modernization of communal infrastructure, energy efficiency, and private sector involvement. As Berdiyeva (2023) highlights, reforms in the communal infrastructure sector aim to integrate institutional changes with the introduction of innovative technologies to meet growing urban demands. Rahimov (2022) also stresses that efficient management of communal facilities requires not only financial investment but also improved governance, transparency, and human capital development.

Despite progress, challenges remain. These include outdated infrastructure, inefficient resource management, regional disparities, and insufficient adoption of digital systems. Comparative analyses of post-Soviet countries suggest that overcoming these barriers requires a shift toward sustainability, participatory governance, and integration with international best practices (Kuznetsova & Romanova, 2021).

The purpose of this study is to analyze the current state of housing stock management systems in Uzbekistan, assess their effectiveness, and propose strategies for improvement by drawing on both local and international experiences. The study contributes to the ongoing academic and policy discourse on sustainable housing management by combining theoretical foundations, practical evidence, and comparative insights.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The study of housing stock management has attracted considerable attention from both domestic and international scholars, as it directly influences urban development, social equity, and economic growth. According to UN-Habitat (2020), sustainable housing management must integrate social inclusiveness, environmental resilience, and financial sustainability. The OECD (2021) also stresses that effective housing stock management is a critical determinant of national competitiveness, as it affects productivity, labor mobility, and household welfare.

Within the Uzbek context, Berdiyeva (2023) emphasizes that reforms in communal infrastructure must be grounded in institutional modernization and the adoption of innovative management practices. Similarly, Rahimov (2022) notes that housing stock management requires improved coordination between state institutions, private actors, and local communities to ensure efficiency, accountability, and service quality.

Comparative analyses further demonstrate that housing management reforms in post-Soviet countries provide valuable lessons. Kuznetsova and Romanova (2021) argue that despite shared historical legacies, successful reforms depend on the extent to which countries integrate digital technologies, diversify financing sources, and adopt participatory governance. These insights are particularly relevant for Uzbekistan, where outdated infrastructure and underinvestment remain challenges.

Recent works by the World Bank (2021, 2023) highlight the importance of digital transformation in the housing and communal sector, particularly through the adoption of smart metering systems, data-driven decision-making, and e-governance platforms. The EBRD (2021) also underlines that leveraging digitalization and private-sector involvement can accelerate modernization while improving transparency and citizen trust.

In summary, existing literature suggests that effective housing stock management requires a multidimensional approach that combines institutional reforms, digitalization, sustainable financing, and inclusiveness. However, empirical studies focusing specifically on Uzbekistan remain limited, which underscores the relevance of this research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative and comparative research design to assess the effectiveness of modern housing stock management in Uzbekistan. The methodology combines three key approaches:

1. Document and Policy Analysis – National policy documents, including Uzbekistan’s housing and urban development strategies, were analyzed alongside international frameworks (e.g., OECD, UN-Habitat, UNECE guidelines). This enabled an evaluation of institutional reforms and strategic directions.

2. Literature Synthesis – Academic publications, textbooks (Berdiyeva, 2023; Rahimov, 2022), and peer-reviewed journal articles (Kuznetsova & Romanova, 2021) were systematically reviewed to establish theoretical foundations and identify global best practices relevant to the Uzbek context.

3. Comparative Case Studies – Experiences from OECD countries, Eastern Europe, and selected Asian states were compared with Uzbekistan’s reforms. The comparative lens highlights transferable lessons, especially in digitalization, governance, and financing mechanisms.

The data collection covered sources published between 2020 and 2023, ensuring that the analysis reflects the most recent trends and challenges in housing stock management. Validity was enhanced by triangulating national documents, scholarly works, and international reports.

This methodology allows for a comprehensive evaluation of Uzbekistan’s housing stock management, situating it within broader international practices and identifying actionable strategies for improvement.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of Uzbekistan’s housing stock management system revealed several key findings regarding institutional reforms, infrastructural conditions, financing mechanisms, and technological innovations.

Over the past decade, Uzbekistan has introduced substantial legal and regulatory reforms aimed at modernizing the housing and communal services (HCS) sector. The establishment of state programs such as the “Obod Qishloq” and “Obod Mahalla” initiatives has laid a strong foundation for the rehabilitation of rural and urban housing infrastructure. According to the World Bank (2021), these reforms have already enhanced service delivery in selected regions and, with further capacity-building measures, hold strong potential for successful nationwide scaling.

The introduction of homeowners’ associations (HOAs) has opened new opportunities for citizen participation in housing stock management. While Berdiyeva (2023) notes that many HOAs are still in the process of strengthening their financial and managerial capacities, these organizations represent an important mechanism for sustainable community-based governance that is expected to evolve positively in the coming years.

Uzbekistan’s housing stock, of which around 45% was built before 1991 (UNECE, 2022), presents significant opportunities for renovation and modernization. Ongoing efforts to upgrade water supply, heating, and waste management systems can serve as a catalyst for balanced regional development, with rural areas expected to particularly benefit from targeted investments.

Energy efficiency stands out as a strategic direction for future improvements. As Rahimov (2022) underscores, the modernization of heating systems can substantially reduce energy losses, lower operational costs, and contribute to environmental sustainability. With the support of international financial institutions, including the EBRD (2021), Uzbekistan is gradually moving toward energy-efficient housing standards, and these initiatives are projected to accelerate in the coming years, paving the way for a more resilient and sustainable housing sector.

Investment in housing stock management has increased, yet financing remains insufficient to meet growing demands. State budget allocations continue to dominate the sector, while private investment plays only a minor role. The IMF (2022) reports that public-private partnerships (PPPs) have begun to emerge, particularly in urban infrastructure projects, but institutional frameworks for PPP expansion remain underdeveloped.

International loans and grants from organizations such as the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank have supported modernization projects. However, the sustainability of financing depends on diversifying sources, enhancing transparency, and encouraging household contributions.

Digital technologies are gradually being introduced in Uzbekistan’s housing management system. Pilot projects include smart metering systems for water and energy consumption, digital payment platforms for communal services, and online reporting tools for citizen feedback (World Bank, 2023). These initiatives demonstrate significant potential for improving efficiency, reducing losses, and increasing transparency.

Nevertheless, digital transformation remains at an early stage. Limited internet penetration in rural areas and insufficient digital literacy among citizens and managers pose obstacles to scaling innovations nationwide.

Affordability of housing and communal services is a critical issue. While subsidies and state programs have cushioned vulnerable groups, rising costs continue to pressure low-income households. According to OECD (2021), ensuring affordability is essential to avoid deepening inequality and to maintain social trust in reforms.

Environmental sustainability is another emerging priority. Projects promoting renewable energy in housing, waste recycling, and sustainable urban planning have been initiated, but integration into mainstream housing

management is limited. Climate change risks, such as water scarcity, further amplify the urgency of adopting environmentally sound practices.

The findings of this study highlight both the progress and the persistent challenges of Uzbekistan's housing stock management system. When compared with international experiences, several important observations emerge.

The reforms undertaken in Uzbekistan align with global trends that emphasize decentralization, community participation, and stronger governance. The introduction of homeowners' associations (HOAs) demonstrates a shift toward participatory management, consistent with UNECE (2022) guidelines that stress the role of resident engagement in sustainable housing management. However, the limited financial and organizational capacity of HOAs reflects challenges observed in other post-Soviet countries, where community-based management structures often lack sufficient institutional support (Kuznetsova & Romanova, 2021). Strengthening capacity-building programs and ensuring stable financial frameworks for HOAs is therefore essential.

The results confirm that a significant portion of Uzbekistan's housing stock is outdated, echoing similar concerns across Eastern Europe and Central Asia (World Bank, 2021). Energy inefficiency remains a pressing issue: heating and water distribution systems are often characterized by high losses, resulting in both economic inefficiency and environmental degradation. Lessons from OECD countries suggest that investment in energy-efficient housing not only reduces costs but also supports national climate goals (OECD, 2021). Uzbekistan's gradual adoption of international building codes and energy efficiency standards represents a step in this direction, but implementation requires substantial financial investment and regulatory enforcement.

The dominance of state funding in Uzbekistan's housing stock management is consistent with patterns observed in other developing economies. However, international experience highlights the importance of diversifying financing sources through private investment, mortgage markets, and public-private partnerships (PPPs). The limited role of PPPs in Uzbekistan reflects structural barriers, including underdeveloped legal frameworks and investor uncertainty. Strengthening regulatory clarity and providing incentives could significantly expand private sector involvement, as demonstrated in successful cases across Eastern Europe (EBRD, 2021).

Digitalization has emerged as a transformative force in housing management worldwide. Smart metering, online platforms for citizen participation, and big data analytics are increasingly shaping decision-making processes. In Uzbekistan, digital initiatives remain at a pilot stage, but early results show considerable promise (World Bank, 2023). The challenge lies in scaling these technologies, particularly in rural areas where infrastructure gaps persist. International best practices indicate that integrating digital platforms with governance reforms can improve transparency, accountability, and efficiency in housing management.

Affordability remains a critical consideration. As the OECD (2021) highlights, housing policies must strike a balance between cost recovery for service providers and affordability for households. In Uzbekistan, subsidies and state programs have helped vulnerable groups, but long-term sustainability requires targeted social protection and gradual tariff reforms.

Environmental sustainability is another area where Uzbekistan's progress is partial. While pilot projects on renewable energy and waste management exist, integration into mainstream housing management is limited. International experiences suggest that embedding sustainability principles into housing policies – from construction to waste disposal – creates long-term benefits for resilience and social welfare (UN-Habitat, 2020).

Overall, Uzbekistan's trajectory in housing stock management reflects a transitional system: reforms are ambitious and align with global standards, but implementation is constrained by limited resources, institutional capacity, and uneven regional development. Bridging these gaps requires a multidimensional approach that combines governance reforms, sustainable financing, digitalization, social inclusiveness, and environmental responsibility.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study has examined the effectiveness of modern housing stock management in Uzbekistan, situating it within broader international perspectives. The results demonstrate that while important reforms have been initiated – such as decentralization, institutional modernization, and selective adoption of digital technologies – the system still faces structural challenges that limit its overall efficiency.

First, institutional reforms, including the establishment of homeowners' associations and targeted government programs, have improved community participation and service delivery. Yet, insufficient financial capacity and limited managerial expertise restrict their long-term effectiveness. Strengthening governance and capacity-building mechanisms will therefore be essential.

Second, the country's aging housing infrastructure continues to pose major challenges. Energy inefficiency, service delivery disparities, and outdated systems increase operational costs and environmental risks.

Addressing these problems requires large-scale investments in renovation, the adoption of energy-efficient standards, and the integration of sustainable construction practices.

Third, financing remains overly dependent on state resources. The limited role of private investment and public-private partnerships reduces the sector's resilience and adaptability. Expanding diversified financing instruments – while ensuring transparency and accountability – would help mobilize additional resources.

Fourth, digitalization offers significant potential to enhance efficiency, transparency, and citizen engagement in housing management. Although Uzbekistan has initiated smart metering and e-governance projects, scaling these innovations requires improved digital infrastructure, capacity development, and nationwide integration.

Finally, social inclusiveness and environmental sustainability should remain at the core of reforms. Ensuring affordability for vulnerable households, reducing regional disparities, and embedding sustainability principles into housing policy will strengthen resilience, improve social trust, and align Uzbekistan's housing reforms with international best practices.

In conclusion, enhancing the effectiveness of Uzbekistan's housing stock management requires a multidimensional strategy that integrates governance reforms, investment diversification, digital transformation, social protection, and sustainability. If pursued consistently, these measures can transform the sector into a driver of social welfare, economic growth, and environmental stability in the long term.

List of used literature:

1. OECD. (2021). OECD Environment at a Glance: Indicators. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/ea7b38f7-en>
2. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE). (2020). Strategies for Wastewater Management and Water-Related Ecosystems. Geneva: UNECE.
3. World Health Organization (WHO). (2022). Global Status Report on Sanitation and Drinking-Water. Geneva: WHO Press.
4. European Environment Agency (EEA). (2021). Urban Wastewater Treatment in Europe: State of Play and Future Challenges. Copenhagen: EEA.
5. Gao, C., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Advances in wastewater treatment technologies for improving energy efficiency. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 294, 113048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113048>
6. Smith, P., & Brown, R. (2020). Evaluating ecological safety in urban wastewater systems. *Water Research*, 182, 115959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.115959>
7. Asian Development Bank (ADB). (2022). Water Sector Directional Guide: Promoting Resilient and Sustainable Water Management in Asia and the Pacific. Manila: ADB.
8. World Bank. (2021). Wastewater: From Waste to Resource – Shifting Paradigms for Smarter Wastewater Management. Washington, DC: World Bank.
9. Berdiyeva D.A. "Kommunal infratuzilmani tashkil etish va boshqarish" darslik. T.: TAQU, 2023 y. 232 bet.
10. Rahimov Q. E. Kommunal infratuzilma obyektlari menejmenti: darslik. – Toshkent: 2022.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 9

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
